
Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

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ABSTRACT	ARTICLE DETAILS
<p>This study aims to compare public policies implemented by Indonesia and Thailand in handling illegal fishing. Illegal fishing is a serious problem faced by both countries, which have fishery resources. Illegal fishing, or illegal fishing, refers to the practice of fishing carried out without a permit or in violation of applicable regulations. Efforts to combat illegal fishing have included stricter enforcement of regulations, increased monitoring, and international cooperation between countries to share information and resources. Community e Policy Innovation, Illegal Fishing, Role of Government Supervision, Community Supervision ngagement and education programs have been implemented to raise awareness about sustainable fishing practices and the long-term benefits of preserving marine ecosystems.</p>	<p>Published On: 18 May 2026</p>
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1. INTRODUCTION

Illegal fishing, or illegal fishing, refers to the practice of fishing carried out without a permit or in violation of applicable regulations. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), illegal fishing includes various activities, such as fishing in prohibited zones, using inappropriate fishing gear, and catching protected species (FAO, 2020). In the context of Indonesia and Thailand, illegal fishing is not only a legal problem, but also a serious challenge to the sustainability of marine resources that are very important for the lives of coastal communities. The impacts of illegal fishing go beyond ecological concerns, damaging local economies and threatening food security for millions of people who rely on fish as a primary source of protein. (Christensen, 2016)

Efforts to combat illegal fishing have included stricter enforcement of regulations, increased oversight, and international cooperation between countries to share information and resources (Puspoayu & Setyowati, 2018). Additionally, community engagement and education programs have been implemented to raise awareness about sustainable fishing practices and the long-term benefits of preserving marine ecosystems. (Amiruddin et al., 2022) These initiatives aim to empower local communities, ensuring they play a vital role in protecting their marine environment while also benefiting economically from sustainable practices. (Amiruddin et al., 2022)

The impacts of illegal fishing are vast and complex. Economically, this practice can result in significant losses for the country. According to a 2017 World Bank report, losses due to illegal fishing worldwide are estimated to reach approximately \$23 billion per year (World Bank, 2017). In Indonesia, illegal fishing threatens the livelihoods of more than 2.8 million fishermen who depend on marine resources. Furthermore, illegal fishing also negatively impacts marine ecosystems. Overfishing can reduce fish populations and disrupt the balance of the ecosystem, which in turn can cause long-term damage to marine habitats (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2021).

Public policy innovation is key to effectively addressing the problem of illegal fishing. Innovative policies must be not only reactive but also proactive in preventing these illegal practices. In Indonesia, for example, the government has implemented stricter policies and utilized modern technology, such as satellite and drone monitoring, to monitor fishing activities at sea (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2021). Meanwhile, Thailand has also implemented policy reforms involving various stakeholders, including fishermen, to create a sustainable fisheries management system. Thus, a comparison of public policy innovations between the two countries is very important to study, in order to find more effective solutions in dealing with illegal fishing.

This study aims to compare public policies implemented by Indonesia and Thailand in handling illegal fishing. Illegal fishing is a serious problem facing both countries, which have rich fishery resources. According to data from the Food and Agriculture

Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

Organization (FAO), approximately 20% of the total global fish catch comes from illegal activities, and Indonesia and Thailand are among the countries with high levels of illegal fishing (FAO, 2020).

In Indonesia, policies to address illegal fishing began to be strengthened in 2014, when President Joko Widodo issued an instruction to eradicate the practice. One significant step was the sinking of vessels involved in illegal fishing, which has become a symbol of the government's firm commitment to protecting marine resources. Data from the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) shows that between 2014 and 2021, more than 500 foreign vessels were sunk as part of this effort (KKP, 2021).

Thailand also faces similar challenges and has implemented various policies to combat illegal fishing. One of the innovations made is the implementation of a strict licensing system for fishermen, as well as the use of monitoring technology such as the Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) to monitor fishing activities. According to a report from the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), Thailand succeeded in reducing the number of illegal fishing cases significantly after implementing this policy (UNODC, 2019).

A comparison between the two policies between these two countries shows that although Indonesia and Thailand are both committed to combating illegal fishing, the approaches and methods applied have significant differences. Indonesia prioritizes firm action through tough law enforcement, while Thailand focuses more on regulation and supervision through technology and licensing. This creates space for further analysis of the effectiveness of each policy in reducing illegal fishing.

Public involvement is crucial in the policy-making process. Public participation in monitoring and reporting illegal fishing activities can be an effective tool in supporting government efforts. Programs that involve local communities in monitoring marine resources, such as those carried out in several areas in Thailand, can be adapted and implemented in Indonesia to increase policy effectiveness. Thus, this study not only aims to compare existing policies, but also provides recommendations that can be implemented to increase the effectiveness of handling illegal fishing in both countries. With the right steps, it is hoped that illegal fishing can be suppressed, so that the sustainability of marine resources can be maintained for the welfare of the community and the ecosystem.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research employed qualitative and comparative methods, using a literature study approach. This approach allowed researchers to explore in-depth the public policies implemented in Indonesia and Thailand in addressing illegal fishing from various relevant literature sources. This article aims to understand the context, process, and impact of existing policies, as well as the innovations implemented by both countries in addressing the problem of illegal fishing.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Public policy is a series of actions taken by the government to achieve specific goals in society. According to Anderson (2015), public policy can be defined as decisions made by the government that focus on issues that affect the wider community. Key characteristics of public policy include multi-stakeholder involvement, complex decision-making processes, and broad impacts on society. In the context of handling *illegal fishing*, public policy must be able to address problems that are not only economic, but also social and environmental. Effective public policy in this area requires collaboration between government agencies, local communities, and international organizations to ensure sustainable practices that protect marine ecosystems while supporting the livelihoods of those who depend on fishing. (Waller, 2013)

Innovation in public policy refers to the development and implementation of new ideas aimed at improving the effectiveness, efficiency, and responsiveness of existing policies. In the context of addressing *illegal fishing*, this innovation can take the form of introducing new technologies, changes in regulations, or new methods of law enforcement. According to Osborne and Brown (2011), public policy innovation can be defined as "the process by which new ideas are generated and implemented within the context of public services to meet the evolving needs of society." In Indonesia and Thailand, innovation in policies to address *illegal fishing* is crucial, given that both countries have vast territorial waters and are hotspots for illegal fishing practices.

Data from the Indonesian Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries shows that between 2015 and 2020, more than 2,000 illegal fishing vessels were apprehended, reflecting the need for innovation in approaches to addressing this issue (KKP, 2021). Thailand, on the other hand, faces similar challenges, with a report from the *Food and Agriculture Organization* (FAO) indicating that approximately 30% of Thailand's total fishing catch originates from illegal practices (FAO, 2020). This suggests that both Indonesia and Thailand need to adapt and develop more innovative policies to address this issue.

Policy innovations can also include collaboration between the government, the private sector, and civil society. For example, in Thailand, the government has partnered with non-governmental organizations to raise awareness of the importance of sustainable fisheries resources. This approach involves not only law enforcement but also education and training for local fishermen on sustainable fishing practices (*Sustainable Fisheries Coalition*, 2020). In Indonesia, a similar initiative is underway, with the government partnering with fishing communities to raise awareness of the importance of preserving marine ecosystems.

Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

3.1. Policy for Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia

Since the early 2000s, Indonesia has faced serious problems related to *illegal fishing*, which has impacted the sustainability of fish resources in national waters. Initial policies implemented by the Indonesian government focused on weak oversight and law enforcement. In 2004, the government began introducing stricter laws, such as Law No. 31 of 2004 concerning Fisheries, which provides a legal basis for prosecuting violations in the fisheries sector. However, the implementation of these policies has often been hampered by a lack of adequate human resources and infrastructure (Patlis, 2007).

However, in recent years, there has been a marked shift towards more effective measures, including increased collaboration with international organizations and the use of technology to monitor fishing activities. (Chapsos et al., 2019) These efforts are beginning to yield positive results, as evidenced by a gradual decline in illegal fishing activities and a more sustainable approach to managing fish stocks. (S, 2018) According to data from the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP), in 2015, Indonesia lost approximately 20 trillion rupiah per year due to *illegal fishing*, indicating that initial policies were not effective enough in addressing the problem (KKP, 2016).

The implementation of this policy still faces many obstacles, including a lack of oversight and weak law enforcement. According to data from the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP), in 2010, approximately 40% of Indonesia's total fish catch came from *illegal fishing practices* (KKP, 2010). However, recent efforts have focused on improving monitoring technology and increasing collaboration with local communities to foster a sense of ownership over marine resources. (Nasirin & Hermawan, 2017) This initiative aims to create a more sustainable fishing industry, ensuring that the environment and local communities benefit from responsible practices. (Nasirin & Hermawan, 2017)

These efforts are crucial in addressing long-standing challenges and fostering a culture of compliance among fishermen, ultimately leading to a healthier marine ecosystem. (Saputra & Purnaweni, 2019)

As awareness of the negative impacts of *illegal fishing* grows, particularly on the economy and ecosystem, the Indonesian government has begun to implement significant policy changes. In 2014, under the leadership of Minister Susi Pudjiastuti, Indonesia adopted a more aggressive approach by launching a campaign to sink foreign vessels caught *fishing illegally*. This step is not only aimed at enforcing the law, but also to demonstrate Indonesia's sovereignty over its marine resources. Data shows that between 2014 and 2019, more than 500 foreign vessels were sunk (KKP, 2019). This bold move garnered international attention and sparked debate about the effectiveness and ethics of such measures, prompting other countries to reconsider their own policies on illegal fishing. (Khairi, 2017)

3.2. Law Enforcement Program

One of the latest policy innovations in handling *illegal fishing* in Indonesia is a stricter law enforcement program. Through court decisions, foreign vessels involved in illegal fishing practices can be seized and used as evidence. This transparent and accountable legal process aims to deter violators. In 2022, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries reported that more than 100 foreign vessels had been seized, demonstrating the government's commitment to enforcing the law (KKP, 2022).

Indonesia also recognizes the importance of international cooperation in addressing *illegal fishing*. In recent years, Indonesia has collaborated with neighboring countries and international organizations to improve surveillance and law enforcement in its waters. For example, Indonesia is involved in the *Regional Plan of Action (RPOA)* program to address *illegal fishing* in the ASEAN region. This collaboration includes not only information exchange but also training for law enforcement officials in the fisheries sector (FAO, 2021). The decision to sink foreign vessels made by Minister Susi Pudjiastuti is one of the most controversial but effective steps in dealing with *illegal fishing*. This action not only confirms Indonesia's sovereignty but also has a positive impact on the country's image in the eyes of the world. For example, after the sinking of the ship, there was an increase in the number of local fishermen reporting *illegal fishing activities* in their area, indicating an increase in public awareness and participation in protecting marine resources (Susi Pudjiastuti, 2019).

3.3. Thailand's *Illegal Fishing* Handling Policy

Thailand is starting to face serious challenges related to *illegal fishing practices* that impact the sustainability of its marine resources. Initial policies implemented focused on weak law enforcement and a lack of clear regulations in the fishing industry. Although Thailand has laws governing fisheries, their implementation is often neglected, and many foreign fishing vessels operate without permits. According to a report from the *Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)*, approximately 50% of Thailand's total fishing catch comes from illegal practices, indicating the urgent need for policy reform (FAO, 2018).

In 2015, Thailand faced significant international pressure regarding *illegal fishing practices*, particularly from the European Union, which threatened to impose sanctions on Thai fisheries products. In response, the Thai government began major reforms to its fisheries policy. One important step is the implementation of a stricter licensing system and increased oversight of vessels operating in Thai waters. According to Thailand's Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, the number of officially registered vessels increased from 18,000 in 2015 to over 23,000 in 2020 (Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, 2020).

Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

Since the policy reforms, Thailand has adopted various initiatives to strengthen law enforcement in the fishing industry. One important step is establishing a National Fisheries Commission to monitor and enforce fisheries regulations. In addition, Thailand also implements modern monitoring technology, such as satellite-based monitoring systems, to track ship activity at sea. Data from the Ministry of Agriculture shows that law violations in the fisheries sector have decreased by 30% in the past two years, thanks to stricter law enforcement efforts (Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives of Thailand, 2022).

In addition to law enforcement, Thailand also involves local communities in efforts to deal with *illegal fishing*. These community-based programs aim to increase community awareness and participation in preserving marine resources. For example, the "Community Fisheries" program involves local fishermen in managing fisheries resources in their area. According to a report from WWF Thailand, community participation in this program has increased by 40% since its launch in 2016, demonstrating that a community-based approach can be an effective solution to addressing *illegal fishing* (WWF Thailand, 2021).

3.4. Comparison of Policy Innovation between Indonesia and Thailand

In the context of addressing *illegal fishing*, Indonesia and Thailand have different legal approaches. In Indonesia, the government has adopted a more repressive approach, imposing severe sanctions on violators. For example, in 2016, Indonesia destroyed 23 foreign vessels caught *fishing illegally* in Indonesian waters (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2016). This move is part of a broader policy to uphold maritime sovereignty and protect dwindling fisheries resources.

Meanwhile, Thailand tends to use a more collaborative approach involving various stakeholders, including the private sector and civil society. For example, following international pressure regarding *illegal fishing practices*, Thailand introduced new laws in 2015 requiring vessel owners to have valid permits and meet certain standards (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2015). This approach demonstrates Thailand's efforts to improve its international image and enhance the sustainability of its fisheries sector.

The effectiveness of regulations in the two countries also shows significant differences. In Indonesia, despite strict policies, numerous challenges remain in law enforcement. According to a 2019 World Bank report, approximately 30% of total fish catch in Indonesia comes from *illegal fishing practices*. This indicates that, despite efforts, regulatory effectiveness still needs to be improved through human resource and technological capacity building.

On the other hand, Thailand has shown progress in reducing *illegal fishing practices* through regulatory reforms. According to a 2019 report from the European Commission, Thailand managed to reduce the number of foreign vessels *fishing illegally* in its waters by 50% within three years of implementing new regulations. This shows that the collaborative approach taken by Thailand can produce more effective results in the long term.

Technological innovation is one of the keys to law enforcement against *illegal fishing* in both countries. Indonesia has implemented satellite-based monitoring technology to monitor fishing activities in their waters. By using a satellite-based monitoring system, the Indonesian government can detect vessels operating without a permit and take swift action to address these violations (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2020). This technology also allows for the collection of more accurate data on fishing activity, which is important for better policy planning.

Meanwhile, Thailand is also utilizing technology in law enforcement efforts. The country has developed a vessel tracking system integrated with data from various sources, including information from the fishing vessels themselves. With this system, authorities can monitor vessel movements and ensure that they do not violate established restrictions (Marine Department of Thailand, 2018). The use of this technology not only increases the efficiency of law enforcement but also provides greater transparency in the fishing industry.

The monitoring systems implemented in Indonesia and Thailand each have their own advantages and disadvantages. In Indonesia, satellite-based monitoring systems provide extensive coverage and the ability to identify vessels operating in remote areas. However, a challenge is the limited trained human resources needed to analyze the resulting data (World Bank, 2020). In addition, corruption issues at the local level can also hinder the effectiveness of monitoring.

On the other hand, Thailand has a more integrated monitoring system, which combines data from various sources. (Peng & Chan, 2015) However, this system also faces challenges in terms of privacy and data protection. The public is often concerned that the data collected may be misused (HE & China, 2010). Therefore, the Thai government needs to explain the benefits of this monitoring system and ensure the security of the collected data (European Commission, 2019). This can help build public trust and encourage cooperation among citizens, which is crucial for the initiative's success.

Furthermore, promoting transparency in the data collection process will further enhance public trust and encourage active participation in governance. (Nekrasov et al., 2013) This can be achieved through regular communication and engagement with the community, ensuring that citizens feel their voices are heard and their concerns are addressed. (Channarong, 2023) This approach not only fosters a sense of ownership among citizens but also empowers them to contribute to the development of policies that affect their lives. (Methakunavudhi, 1998)

Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

Public Participation in Policy

Community involvement in policies to address illegal fishing is crucial for long-term success. In Indonesia, community participation in monitoring fisheries resources remains limited. While there are several local initiatives involving communities, such as community-based fisheries management programs, the challenge is a lack of support and understanding from the central government (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2021). This leaves communities feeling alienated from decision-making processes related to the resources they manage.

In contrast, Thailand has successfully engaged communities in fisheries management through various education and training programs. For example, the Thai government collaborates with non-governmental organizations to provide training to fishermen on sustainable fishing practices and the importance of protecting marine ecosystems (FAO, 2020). This involvement not only raises public awareness but also fosters a sense of ownership over existing fisheries resources.

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play an important role in tackling *illegal fishing* in both countries. In Indonesia, NGOs such as Walhi (Indonesian Forum for the Environment) play an active role in policy advocacy and monitoring of *illegal fishing practices*. They are also involved in community education programs to raise awareness about the importance of sustainable fisheries resources (Walhi, 2021). However, the challenge faced is resistance from certain parties who feel threatened by these monitoring efforts.

In Thailand, NGOs also play a role in supporting government policies regarding illegal fishing. Organizations such as Greenpeace Thailand are active in campaigns to increase transparency in the fishing industry and support sustainable fishing practices. They are also involved in training programs for fishermen to reduce *illegal fishing practices* (Greenpeace, 2020). With NGO involvement, both Indonesia and Thailand can increase the effectiveness of policies to address illegal fishing through a collaborative approach.

Collaborative Strategy between Countries

Addressing *illegal fishing* is a transboundary issue that requires international cooperation. Indonesia and Thailand, as countries that share the same territorial waters, have a significant opportunity to develop collaborative strategies to address illegal fishing. One initial step that can be taken is to establish a regional cooperation forum involving ASEAN countries to share information and best practices in fisheries law enforcement.

This forum can serve as a *platform* for exchanging data on illegal fishing activities, as well as for coordinating law enforcement operations. By sharing information about vessels suspected of *illegal fishing*, countries in the region can increase the effectiveness of their actions. For example, in the collaboration between Indonesia and Malaysia, the two countries succeeded in capturing a number of illegal fishing vessels operating in their waters thanks to the rapid exchange of information (ASEAN, 2022).

In addition, collaboration in training and capacity building for law enforcement officers is also very important. Indonesia and Thailand can help each other improve the capabilities of their law enforcement officers through joint training programs. By improving the ability of officers to detect and address *illegal fishing practices*, both countries can be more effective in protecting their marine resources.

Cooperation can also be expanded to include economic aspects, such as developing sustainable markets for fishery products. By creating an integrated market among ASEAN countries, legally and sustainably produced fishery products will be more accessible to consumers across the region. This will not only improve the welfare of fishers but also encourage more responsible fishing practices.

Finally, Indonesia and Thailand must involve civil society and the private sector in this collaborative effort. By involving local fishermen, non-governmental organizations, and industry players, the resulting policies will be more inclusive and acceptable to all parties. Strong cooperation between the government, communities, and the private sector will create strong synergy in efforts to address illegal fishing in the region. By developing a strong collaborative strategy, Indonesia and Thailand can not only address the challenge of *illegal fishing* but also build a foundation for sustainable marine resources in Southeast Asia. Effective cooperation will be key to achieving the shared goal of protecting marine ecosystems and improving the well-being of fishing communities.

4. CONCLUSION

A comparative analysis of public policy innovations implemented to address illegal fishing in Indonesia and Thailand. Both countries face similar challenges in addressing illegal fishing practices, but their approaches differ significantly. In Indonesia, the government has launched various policies, including a fishing moratorium, strict law enforcement, and the use of modern technology to monitor fishing activities. On the other hand, Thailand has focused on comprehensive reform of its fishing industry, adopting a more monitoring and certification-based approach. Through its "Thailand's Fisheries Improvement Project," the country is working to increase transparency and sustainability in the fisheries sector. Both countries need to continue innovating their policies to address illegal fishing. Indonesia, with its more aggressive approach, needs to consider integrating information and communication technology into its monitoring and reporting systems. The use of drones and satellites for water monitoring can improve the effectiveness of law enforcement. Furthermore, collaboration with local communities and fishermen can help build awareness and

Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

support for implemented policies. Meanwhile, Thailand needs to strengthen its regulatory framework and improve its oversight capacity in the fisheries sector. Certification and sustainability-based approaches should be expanded to include more fishermen and fishing companies. By increasing access to training and resources, Thailand can ensure that sustainable fishing practices become the norm, not the exception. This will not only help reduce illegal fishing but also enhance the reputation of Thai fishery products in the international market.

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Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

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Comparison of Public Policy Innovations in Handling Illegal Fishing in Indonesia with Handling Illegal Fishing in Thailand

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